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Title: TREX1 variants in Sjogren's syndrome related lymphomagenesis

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Abstract: ABSTRACT

Genetic variants of the three-prime repair exonuclease 1 (TREX1) -an exonuclease involved in DNA repair and degradation- have been previously found to increase susceptibility to Aicardi Goutieres syndrome, familial chilblain lupus and systemic lupus erythematosus. We aimed to explore whether TREX1 common variants could influence the risk of primary Sjogren's syndrome (SS) and SS-related lymphoma. Three single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) of the TREX1 gene (rs11797, rs3135941 and the rs3135945) were evaluated in 229 SS, 89 SS-lymphoma (70 SS-MALT and 19 SS non-MALT) and 240 healthy controls by PCR-based assays. In available 52 peripheral blood and 26 minor salivary gland tissues from our SS cohort, mRNA expression of type I interferon (IFN) related genes and TREX1 was determined by real-time PCR. Significantly decreased prevalence of rs11797 A minor allele was detected in SS patients complicated by non-MALT lymphoma compared to controls (OR [95% CI]: 0.4 [0.2-0.9], p-value: 0.02). SS patients carrying the rs11797 AA genotype had increased prevalence of type I IFN related gene mRNA expression in minor salivary gland tissues. These data support genetically related dampened type I IFN production as an additional mechanism for SS-related lymphomagenesis.

June 28th, 2019

Prof. Timothy Niewold

Editor of Special Issue

Type I interferon in Human Disease

Cytokine

Dear Dr Niewold,

Attached please find our revised manuscript entitled "***TREX1 variants in Sjogren's syndrome related lymphomagenesis***" by A. Nezos et al submitted for publication as ***original article***, according to the reviewers' suggestions. In the current work we revealed a potential contribution of the TREX1 rs11797 gene variant in the pathogenesis of Sjogren's syndrome (SS)-related lymphomas, with the minor A allele and corresponding genotype, found to occur less frequently in a subset of SS patients complicated by non-MALT lymphomas compared to healthy controls. We have additionally shown that in the SS setting, the TREX1 rs11797 AA genotype is associated with high type I interferon (IFN) related transcript levels in minor salivary gland tissues. Given the reduced frequency of the rs11797 variant in the non-MALT SS subgroup, we postulate that defective type I IFN production (known for its anti-proliferative properties) could represent a potential mechanism of TREX-1 related lymphomagenesis in the context of SS.

We confirm that the manuscript is original research that has not been published, is not under consideration elsewhere, all of the authors participated in the preparation and approved the manuscript for submission. We also confirm that we have obtained the required ethical approval by the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Medical School Ethics Committee (approved No. 6337), Athens, Greece, that they have given necessary attention to ensure the integrity of the work, and agree to bear the applicable publication charges if their manuscript is accepted for publication. We declare no conflict of interests.

Thank you for considering our manuscript.

Yours sincerely,

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Reviewers' comments:

Reviewer #1:

This study has investigated the TREX1 polymorphism in cohorts of primary Sjogren's syndrome patients and revealed a potential correlation between variance rs11797 and SS-non-MALT patient group, as well as anti-Ro/SSA autoantibodies and specific metrics of type I IFN related genes in the minor salivary gland. Overall the rationale was reasonable and stated explicitly. However several critical concerns from the data presentation and analysis need to be addressed as detailed below:

1. given the overwhelming negative data presented here, in particular, no difference was observed in TREX1 variants between SS, SS-lymphoma, and HC, the data from a small subset of SS-lymphoma (non-MALT, N=19) rang the bell of caution. Comparing a small group with a large group that is ten times larger (N=19, vs. N=240) could introduce certain variation merely due to the vast difference between the sample size of the two groups. Either more samples are needed to balance out this difference, or additional measurements are necessary to support this observation given the weakness of the study design.

We fully agree with the reviewer's comment and we have already acknowledged this limitation in the discussion section. Nevertheless, given the rarity of these non MALT lymphomas associated with SS, we believe that these data are relevant since they might provide some pathogenetic clues regarding non MALT lymphomas in the setting of SS. Furthermore, to address this issue, an independent Italian cohort including 7 non MALT lymphomas confirmed the rarity of the rs11797 AA genotypic variant in the SS non MALT group. These data are included in the supplemental table 1.

2. From the results, it reads like a pick-and-choose story: only the positive data was highlighted, yet negative data was reported but not factored into conclusion/discussion.

We have now included negative data in the conclusion/discussion section as suggested.

-For instance, there is no difference regarding TREX1 expression level among the different variants. How does TREX1 function overall? How, if indeed it is true, does variant rs11797 leads to SS-non-MALT if its expression level was not changed?

TREX1 mRNA levels were not affected by the rs11797 variant in line with previously published results [1]. However, in a recent report, alteration of the rate at which mRNA is translated by the ribosome (known as ribosome-mediated translational attenuation program) has been shown to be affected by the rs11797 variant resulting in potential alteration of final protein conformation and function [2].

This information is now inserted in the discussion section.

-Regarding anti-Ro/SSA autoantibodies, only SS carries of A was presented, however, at this point, it seems only SS-non-MALT patients (not all SS patients) were relevant. Same applies to IFN related gene expression in MSG. Why showing SS patient, but not SS-non-MALT patients? Further, in the later experiment, the patients were chosen for carrying rs11797 AA variant, not A allele. This swift change of subject makes it hard to grasp the validity of the dataset.

To clarify the issue raised by the referee 1, we reanalyzed our data comparing the frequency of anti-Ro/SSA antibodies according to the rs11797 AA genotypic variant as well as the presence or type of lymphoma. As shown in the newly inserted supplementary figure 1, non statistically significant associations between groups were detected when we reanalyzed the data according to the reviewer's suggestion. This information is now added in the results section.

Moreover, we emphasize the association of the rs11797 AA genotypic variant with type I IFN responses in the whole SS group, to further support the validity of our findings and given the non availability of MSG tissues derived from SS non MALT patients. The reduced frequency of an otherwise "autoimmune variant" in the non MALT SS subgroup might imply defective immune surveillance functions leading to malignant transformation. These data reinforce our previous findings revealing dampened IFN α transcripts in salivary glands derived from SS patients with lymphoma and are compatible with recently published data supporting an abrogating effect of TREX1 on overexpression in type I IFN responses by cancer cells receiving a single high-dose radiation leading to their survival related to reduced immunogenicity [3].

A relevant comment is now added in the discussion section.

-Regarding data selection, if only anti-Ro/SSA autoantibodies but not other clinical or laboratory features were associated, what does that mean? Would the endpoint of autoantibody trumps other clinical features or what kind of reconciliation can be made based on this complex observation? Both positive AND negative results need to be taken into consideration when concluding and discussing whether the variant is correlated or not with the SS-non-MALT disease.

We fully agree with the reviewer's concerns and therefore in the revised manuscript associations with clinical and serological features are separately presented in the SS-non lymphoma, the SS-MALT and SS-non MALT subgroups according to the presence or absence of the AA rs11797 genotype. As shown in the newly inserted supplemental figure 1 and tables 2-5, no significant associations in clinical or serological features were demonstrated when data were separately analyzed.

Answers to reviewer's 3 comments

Reviewer #3:

In this paper, the authors aimed to explore the influence of TREX1 common variants in SS related lymphomagenesis. Authors reports that their study supports the role of specific TREX1 variants in SS related non-MALT lymphoma, possibly through dampened type I IFN production. There is very sparse literature-discussing association of TREX1 variants related to SS related lymphoma and hence this kind of study is interesting. Currently this study looks like more like genetic epidemiology/genotype association study showing frequency of various TREX1 variant alleles in different subgroups of SS patients and HC patients. However, this study needs additional functional studies to support the association of these variants in SS related lymphomagenesis. Their current Type I IFN expression studies are not convincing enough to support the role TREX1 variants in SS-related lymphomagenesis.

We would like to thank reviewer 3 for his/her encouraging comments. We agree with the reviewer's suggestion that functional studies will be needed to specifically link the TREX1 variants to mechanisms of lymphomagenesis. Please see our comments below

My more specific comments are

*** Authors say the TREX1 variants they studied here are more common however, for one of the variant rs3135945 frequency of variant allele is very low making it difficult to do comparison among subgroups due to low number of subjects in each subgroup.**

As already mentioned in the introduction section, the selection of these variants was based on previous studies in lupus and the rarity of the rs3135945 had been recognized. Therefore the low frequency detected in our Sjogren's syndrome cohort is compatible with previous studies in lupus. This clarification is now added in the introduction and discussion section.

*** It is difficult to read and understand figures in current format and high-resolution figures will be helpful.**

We have now increased the resolution of the figures as suggested.

*** In discussion section, authors can write a paragraph proposing the functional studies that can be performed in future to support their current study.**

A new paragraph has now been added in the discussion section as follows:

“In further studies, our aim is to explore whether *trex1* exonuclease activity is affected by the presence of the rs11797 *TREX1* gene variant using commercially available 3' to 5' Exonuclease Activity Assays in isolated PBMCs from wild type and mutant carriers. Furthermore, given the implication of TREX1 in genomic instability [4] - a previously proposed

mechanism for lymphomagenesis [5] - intrinsic DNA damage will be assessed using the comet assay in the same samples.”

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TREX1 variants in Sjogren's syndrome related lymphomagenesis

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ABSTRACT

Genetic variants of the three-prime repair exonuclease 1 (*TREX1*) -an exonuclease involved in DNA repair and degradation- have been previously found to increase susceptibility to Aicardi Goutieres syndrome, familial chilblain lupus and systemic lupus erythematosus. We aimed to explore whether *TREX1* common variants could influence the risk of primary Sjogren's syndrome (SS) and SS-related lymphoma. Three single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) of the *TREX1* gene (rs11797, rs3135941 and the rs3135945) were evaluated in 229 SS, 89 SS-lymphoma (70 SS-MALT and 19 SS non-MALT) and 240 healthy controls by PCR-based assays. In available 52 peripheral blood and 26 minor salivary gland tissues from our SS cohort, mRNA expression of type I interferon (IFN) related genes and *TREX1* was determined by real-time PCR. Significantly decreased prevalence of rs11797 A minor allele was detected in SS patients complicated by non-MALT lymphoma compared to controls (OR [95% CI]: 0.4 [0.2-0.9], p-value: 0.02). SS patients carrying the rs11797 AA genotype had increased type I IFN related gene mRNA expression in minor salivary gland tissues. These data support genetically related dampened type I IFN production as an additional mechanism for SS-related lymphomagenesis.

Key words: Three-prime repair exonuclease 1 (*TREX1*), lymphoma, Sjogren's syndrome (SS), single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), genetics

1. Introduction

Primary Sjogren's syndrome (SS) is a chronic autoimmune disease characterized by lymphocytic infiltration of the exocrine glands, mainly salivary and lacrimal resulting in oral and ocular dryness [1]. One of the major complications among SS patients is the development of B-cell non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (NHL) -mainly mucosa associated lymphoid tissue lymphoma type (MALT)-, though other lymphoma subtypes, including diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL) and nodal marginal zone lymphoma (NMZL), have been also described [2-8].

The pathogenesis of the syndrome remains to be elucidated, although the contribution of both genetic and environmental factors (infections, stress, hormones) has been previously documented [9]. Over the last decades, cumulative evidence suggests activation of the interferon (IFN) pathways as a key event in the pathogenesis of both SS and SS related lymphomas [10-12]. Endogenous nucleic acids, including Long Interspersed Nuclear Element-1 (LINE-1), -either due to genetic defects in enzymes of nucleic acid metabolism or epigenetic alterations such as methylation- have been recently proposed as potential triggers of type I IFN activation in systemic autoimmunity through activation of Toll-like receptor-dependent and independent pathways [13-17]. Though the mechanism of lymphomagenesis in the setting of SS has not been clearly defined, genetic alterations leading to abnormal B-cell function, methylation defects and DNA damage have been previously postulated [16, 18, 19]. A recent study from our group indicated low IFN α levels in minor salivary gland tissues derived from primary SS patients complicated by lymphoma, implying loss of IFN α mediated immunosurveillance against malignant transformation as a potential contributor to lymphomagenesis in these patients [12].

Three-prime repair exonuclease 1 (TREX1) is an exonuclease (the major exonuclease in mammals) involved in both endogenous nucleic acid clearance [20, 21] and maintenance of genomic stability through replication, repair and recombination mechanisms [22, 23]. Recent studies revealed TREX1 genetic defects in conditions hallmarked by activation of the type I IFN pathway, including Aicardi-Goutieres syndrome (AGS) [13, 24-26], familial chilblain lupus [27, 28], systemic lupus erythematosus

(SLE) [13, 24, 29-32] and systemic sclerosis [33]. Particularly, the rs11797 *TREX1* variant -a common synonymous single nucleotide polymorphism-, the 5'UTR rs3135941 *TREX1* variant and the rare variant rs3135945 have been previously evaluated in a large multi-ancestral lupus patient group [29].

The rs11797 and the rs3135941 were found to contribute to a risk *TREX1* haplotype among European lupus patients with neurological manifestations (the rs11797 was found as the major contributor variant) [29]. Additionally, a growing body of evidence points towards a significant role for the *TREX1* molecule in cancer biology and regulation of anti-tumor immunity [34, 35]. Nevertheless, *TREX1* related genetic and expression data in SS- a disease model at the crossroad of autoimmunity and cancer [36, 37]- are scarce.

In the current study we aimed to investigate whether known *TREX1* variants, previously shown to increase SLE susceptibility, are associated with SS and SS-related lymphoma. Associations of these variants with expression of type I IFN related genes were also sought.

2. Patients and Methods

2.1. Patients

In the present case-control study DNA derived from 318 primary SS patients [89 complicated with lymphoma (SS-lymphoma) and 229 without lymphoma (SS)] and 240 apparently healthy individuals served as a healthy control (HC) group. The mean age \pm standard deviation (SD) and the female percentage in our study participant groups were 62.1 \pm 12.4 years and 93.3% females in SS-lymphoma, 62.0 \pm 13.5 years and 93.3% females in SS and 56.5 \pm 13.2 years and 87.5% females in HC. All patients were followed in the Outpatient Rheumatology Clinic of the Department of Pathophysiology, School of Medicine, University of Athens, in the Institute of Systemic Autoimmune and Neurological Diseases and the Department of Rheumatology, General Hospital of Athens "G. Gennimatas", Athens, Greece. All patients fulfilled the 2002 American/European criteria for the classification of primary SS [38]. The

study was approved by National and Kapodistrian University of Athens Medical School Ethics Committee (No. 6337). All subjects gave informed consent in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. All methods were performed in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations.

Lymphoma diagnosis was based on World Health Organization classification criteria. In the current study, SS-lymphoma patients were further classified into two main groups: the SS-MALT group (70 patients/ 83.3% females, age: mean±SD: 60.7 ± 12.1 years) and the SS non-MALT group (19 patients/ 100% females, age: mean±SD: 67.1± 12.4 years) including 12 patients with DLBCL, 4 with NMZL, 2 small lymphocytic lymphoma (SLL) and 1 T-cell lymphoma (TCL).

In order to assess the ancestry of the study participants, detailed data on family history was collected as previously described[18]. The vast majority (>99%) of both patient and control populations were of Greek ancestry.

Demographics and disease-related clinical and laboratory features were recorded after thorough chart review. Clinical characteristics included subjective and objective measures of oral and ocular dryness (Schirmer's test, Rose-Bengal stain); salivary gland enlargement (SGE); arthralgias/myalgias, arthritis; Raynaud's phenomenon; palpable purpura; lymphadenopathy and lymphoma development. Documented laboratory features included leucopenia [white blood cell count (WBC) <3000/μl in three independent measurements], the presence of ANA (≥1/320), RF positivity (>20IU/ml), anti-Ro/SSA and anti-La/SSB antibodies, C4 complement levels, cryoglobulinemia and hypergammaglobulinemia (>18%), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), β2-Microglobulin and immunoglobulins IgG, IgA and IgM. Finally, histopathological features in minor salivary gland (MSG) biopsies including Chisolm [39] and Tarpley [40] scores were also recorded.

An independent Italian cohort of 86 patients with primary SS, according to the American–European Consensus Group classification criteria [38], who were being followed up in the University Hospital Rheumatology Clinic in Udine, Italy, was also included in the study. These patients with primary SS were further classified as follows: 52 patients with primary SS (mean ± SD age 63.9±12.8 years), 27

primary SS patients complicated by MALT lymphoma (mean \pm SD age 59.7 \pm 11.6 years) and 7 primary SS patients complicated by non-MALT lymphoma (mean \pm SD age 69.3 \pm 2.8 years), including 4 DLBCL, 2 NMZL and 1 large lymphocytic lymphoma (LLC).

2.2.1 DNA extraction

Genomic DNA was extracted from whole blood samples using the Nucleospin Blood QuickPure kit (Macherey-Nagel GmbH & Co, Germany), according to the manufacturer's instructions. DNA concentration was measured by Biospec-Nano spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan).

2.2.2. *TREX1* gene variants genotyping

We examined single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) of the *TREX1* gene previously reported in lupus patients: the synonymous variation rs11797 (A>G, p.Tyr177Tyr), the 5'UTR rs3135941 (C>T, NG_009820.1:g.5439T>C) and the synonymous variation rs3135945 (G>A, p.Leu340Leu).

The SNPs were tested by Real time PCR Probe based assay. Amplification was carried out in a total volume of 15 μ L with the KAPA PROBE FAST Bio-Rad iCycler master mix (Kapa Biosystems, Germany) containing 0.3 μ M of each primer and 0.4 μ M of each probe for all the SNPs and 50ng of genomic DNA in the BIORAD IQ5 cycler (BIORAD, USA). Primers and probes were designed and synthesized by VBC Genomics (Vienna, Austria) and included the rs3135941 forward primer: CACGCCAAGTTTCACTCC, reverse primer: GCCACACTCACCGTAGCA, probe: FAM-GCGGGAGAGTGTGCAGCCG-BHQ1 for T at the SNP-position and probe HEX-GCGGGAGAGCGTGCAGCCG-BHQ1 for C at the SNP-position, the rs11797 forward primer: GAGTCTGGAGGGGACTGC, reverse primer: TGTGTGGATAGCATCACTGC, probe FAM-CTGCCTAGGCTATAGCTCTTCCTT-BHQ1 for A at the SNP-position and probe HEX-CTGCCTAGGCTGTAGCTCTTCCTT -BHQ1 for G at the SNP-position. The polymorphism rs3135945 was evaluated with specific commercially available primer and probe set (Taqman SNP Genotyping Assays, Assay ID: C_32390141_10, Applied Biosystems, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA).

Direct bidirectional Sanger sequencing was performed for 8 samples for each SNP to validate the genotyping results and two reference samples of each genotype were included in each assay. Samples were tested twice for all SNPs.

2.2.3 Quantification of type I IFN inducible genes and *TREX1* mRNA in peripheral blood samples derived from SS patients and HC

Available cDNA from 52 peripheral blood (PB) samples derived from SS patients of the present cohort and nine age/sex matched HC was subjected to Real Time PCR for *GAPDH*, three type I IFN related genes (IFIGs) [myxovirus (influenza virus) resistance 1 (*MX-1*), forward primer: TACCAGGACTACGAGATTG and reverse primer: TGCCAGGAAGGTCTATTAG, IFN- induced protein with tetratricopeptide repeats 1 (*IFIT1*), forward primer: CTCCTTGGGTTTCGTCTATAAATTG and reverse primer: AGTCAGCAGCCAGTCTCAG and the TNF receptor-associated factor 3 (*TRAF3*) forward primer: GACGCCAGTTTTTGTCCCTG and reverse primer: ACGATGCTCTCTTGACACGC]. *TREX1* mRNA expression was also quantified using primers purchased from Qiagen (Hs_TREX1_1_SG QuantiTect Primer Assay 249900).

2.2.4. Quantification of type I IFN related genes in salivary gland tissues derived from SS patients

Available cDNA from minor salivary glands (MSG) was obtained from 26 SS patients of the present cohort and two sicca controls and subjected to Real Time PCR for *GAPDH*, *MX-1*, *IFIT-1*, *TRAF3* as well as the TNF-related apoptosis-inducing ligand (*TRAIL*) pro-apoptotic gene (forward primer GTTGGCTAACTGACCTGGAAAG and reverse primer TGGTTGTGGCTGCTCTACTC), as previously described [12].

2.3. Statistics

Allele and genotype frequencies in patients and HC were determined for each variant by SHEsis and SNPStats software [41, 42]. We also used the SHEsis software platform (<http://analysis.bio-x.cn>) for

analysis of linkage disequilibrium (LD), haplotype construction and genetic association at polymorphism loci [41]. Genotype frequencies in control subjects for each SNP were tested for departure from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium. Genotype frequencies for each SNP were compared in patients and HC using the χ^2 test. ORs and corresponding 95% CIs were estimated by logistic regression. Adjustment for the effects of age and gender was also performed. The five genetic models (codominant, dominant, recessive, overdominant and additive) were also determined [42]. Similarly, genotype frequencies for each SNP were compared between patients and HC, as described above. Comparisons of type I IFN related genes according to different *TREX1* genotypes were performed by Mann Whitney test, by SPSS v.21 and GraphPad Prism software. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. For the genetic study, the threshold for p-value significance is set to p: 0.025 (0.05/2, as comparisons of two SNPs were performed).

3. Results

3.1. Allele and genotype analysis in SS, SS-lymphoma patients and HC

No statistically significant differences in allele and genotype frequencies of the *TREX1* variants rs11797, rs3135941 and rs3135945 were detected between primary SS, SS-lymphoma or HC ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons, Tables 1 and 2).

3.2. Allele and genotype analysis in SS-MALT, SS non-MALT and HC groups

We next compared the prevalence of the *TREX1* rs11797 and rs3135941 variants in SS-lymphoma subgroups, SS-MALT and SS non-MALT, to both SS and HC. As shown in Tables 3 and 4, no statistically significant differences in the prevalence of the rs11797 and rs3135941 *TREX1* variants were found between SS-MALT and HC groups in both allele (Table 3) and genotype analysis (Table 4) ($p > 0.05$). In contrast, the A allele of the rs11797 *TREX1* variant was found to be significantly less

frequent in SS non-MALT patients compared to HC (31.6% vs 51.3%, OR [95% CI]: 0.4 [0.2-0.9], p-value: 0.02, Table 3). After age and sex adjustment, the corresponding OR [95% CI] was found to be 0.4 [0.2-0.8], p-value: 0.008. No differences in the frequencies of the rs3135941 allelic variants were found between groups ($p > 0.05$). Accordingly, the prevalence of the AA genotype of the rs11797 *TREX1* variant was significantly lower in SS non-MALT patients compared to HC (10.5% vs 27.5%, additive model: OR [95%CI]: 0.5 [0.2-0.9], $p = 0.02$), while no other significant differences were detected for the rs3135941 variant (Table 4). No statistically significant differences in the distribution of the *TREX1* variants between SS-MALT and SS non-MALT patients were detected (Tables 3 and 4). The *TREX1* rs11797 and rs3135941 variants are in linkage disequilibrium ($D' = 0.358$, $r^2 = 0.025$, $p < 0.001$) and form 4 common haplotypes (frequency for both groups $> 3\%$). The frequency of the *TREX1* GC haplotype was significantly different between HC and SS non-MALT patients (Table 5, global p-value: 0.04). This difference is mainly attributed to the increased frequency of the GC haplotype (alleles for rs11797 and rs3135941, respectively) in SS non-MALT compared to HC (21.1% vs 10.3%, OR [95%CI]: 2.3 [1.01~5.4], p-value: 0.04). Though no statistically significant differences were detected between non-MALT SS groups and HC in regard to rs3135941 C allele possibly related to the small number of patients, the increased frequency of the latter and the corresponding CC genotype in the non-MALT SS group compared to HC (Tables 3 and 4), might contribute to the observed associations with the GC but not the GT haplotype. Finally, no significant differences in the prevalence of the studied *TREX1* variants among SS, SS-MALT and SS non-MALT subgroups were found ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons, data not shown). We next wished to replicate these findings in an independent Italian cohort. As shown in the Supplementary table 1, in line with our observations, none of the seven SS non-MALT patients displayed the rs11797 AA genotype. Moreover, the prevalence of the AA genotype of the rs11797 *TREX1* variant was similar in both SS and SS-MALT groups (25 and 18.5%) respectively. However, due to the small number of patients related to disease rarity, no statistically significant associations were detected between groups.

3.4. No association between *TREX1* variants and *TREX1* mRNA expression in SS derived PB and MSG samples

TREX1 mRNA expression in both PB and MSG tissues did not differ among patients with different *TREX1* genotypes (Fig. 1A, C). Of note, *TREX1* mRNA expression in PB was found to be increased in patients with SS independently of lymphoma status compared to HC (Fig 1B), although such difference was not detected in MSG tissues (Fig. 1D).

3.4. Associations of *TREX1* polymorphisms with clinical features of SS

We next sought to explore whether *TREX1* variants are associated with distinct SS phenotypic and serological features. No significant associations were observed between SS patients carrying the AA genotype of the rs11797 variation versus rs11797 GG and AG genotype carriers apart from marginally higher white blood cell count, ($p=0.06$) and β 2-microglobulin levels ($p=0.07$) as well as reduced RF positivity ($p=0.06$) (Supplemental figure 1, Supplementary Table 2). Similarly, no differences in the frequency of disease related clinical or laboratory features were observed between SS patients carrying the rs3135941 CC genotype compared to those carrying TT and TC genotypes (Supplementary Table 3). Moreover, in the context of SS non MALT, patients carrying either the AA rs11797 or the CC rs3135941 risk variants did not differ in phenotypic and serological features compared to rs11797 GG and GA or rs3135941 TT and TC carriers, respectively (Supplemental figure 1, Supplementary Tables 4 and 5).

3.5. Association of *TREX1* variants with type I IFN related gene expression in SS derived PB and MSG samples

Given the well-known association of *TREX1* mutations with heightened IFN α levels in Aicardi-Goutieres syndrome patients[43], we next sought to explore whether *TREX1* rs11797 and rs3135941

variants are associated with type I IFN related gene expression in PB and MSG tissues derived from SS patients. While no statistically significant association was found between type I IFN related gene expression and the rs11797 and rs3135941 variants in PB (Fig. 2A-C), an increase in IFN related gene expression (*IFIT1*, *MX1*, *TRAF3* and *TRAIL-M*) was revealed in MSG tissues derived from SS patients carrying the rs11797 AA variant (Figs. 2D-G).

4. Discussion

In the current study, no statistically significant differences were detected in the frequency of three *TREX1* gene variants tested (rs11797, rs3135941, rs3135945) between SS patients with or without lymphoma and healthy controls. However, we revealed a potential contribution of the *TREX1* rs11797 gene variant in the pathogenesis of SS-related lymphomas, with the minor A allele and corresponding genotype found to occur less frequently in a subset of SS patients complicated by non-MALT lymphomas compared to HC. We have additionally shown that in the SS setting, the *TREX1* rs11797 AA genotype is associated with high type I IFN related transcript levels in MSG tissues. Given the reduced frequency of the rs11797 variant in the non-MALT SS subgroup, we postulate that defective type I IFN production (known for its anti-proliferative properties) could represent a potential mechanism of *TREX1* related lymphomagenesis in the context of SS. No differences between *TREX1* expression and the gene variants tested were observed. These data imply that this variant might be related to activation of type I IFN pathway affecting the function of the enzyme rather than its expression.

While several *TREX1* genetic alterations have been previously associated with AGS and SLE [13, 24-26], data on SS are rather limited. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study to evaluate the presence of *TREX1* genetic variants in a cohort of primary SS patients, including a large number of patients with lymphoma. In accord with previous studies of SS patients of European ancestry (German and Italian) [30, 44], no significant differences in frequency of the rs11797 and the rs3135941 variants

between SS patients and controls were detected. However, a potential association with lymphoma development in the setting of SS, and particularly of the non-MALT type, has not been previously explored.

In regard to the rs3135945 *TREX1* variant -a rare variant, with an ill-defined pathogenetic role- no differences were detected between patients and controls, in accord with previously published results [29, 30, 33]. Isolated SS and SLE cases from an Italian study [30] and only one out of our 257 SS patients and none of our HC were shown to carry this polymorphism.

The rs11797 SNP has been previously studied in SLE, SS and SSc and represents a synonymous variation [29, 30, 33]. According to the HapMap database and the 1000 Genomes project, the variant seems to be a benign common polymorphism in the general population. In patients with lupus the minor A allele of rs11797 has been found to occur more frequently in a disease subset characterized by neuropsychiatric manifestations [29, 45] already linked to high type I IFN responses [46] [47]. Though *TREX1* mRNA levels were not affected by rs11797 variation in line with previously published results [48], in a recent report, alteration of the rate at which mRNA is translated by the ribosome (known as ribosome-mediated translational attenuation program) has been shown to be affected by the rs11797 variant with potential implications in the final protein conformation and function [49], leading eventually to augmented type I responses [43, 46].

The reduced frequency of an otherwise “autoimmune variant” in the non MALT SS subgroup might imply defective immune surveillance functions leading to malignant transformation. These data reinforce our previous findings revealing dampened IFN α transcripts in salivary glands derived from SS patients with lymphoma [12]. The anti-proliferative role of type I interferons is well established through activation of cytotoxic T and NK cells and induction of pro-apoptotic mechanisms[50]. In a recent report, it was shown that radiation induced miR-103 downregulates *TREX1* expression in endothelial cells leading to decreased angiogenesis and production of pro-inflammatory mediators including IFNs, which in turn upregulate the apoptotic molecules Fas and TRAIL in malignant cells [50]. Similarly,

TREX1-mutated lymphocytes derived from an Aicardi-Goutières syndrome patient in co-culture with neuroblastoma cells and vascular endothelial cells in the presence of IFN α restrained the growth of neuroblastoma and endothelial cells, decreasing angiogenesis [51]. Finally, an abrogating effect of overexpressed *TREX1* in type I IFN responses by cancer cells that have received a single high-dose radiation resulting in radiation resistance and tumor cell survival related to reduced immunogenicity of cancer cells [35].

There are a number of limitations however that warrant attention in the present study. First, the small patient sample size, particularly the SS non-MALT group, which limits its statistical power. To address this issue, an independent Italian cohort including 7 non MALT lymphomas confirmed the rarity of the rs11797 AA genotypic variant in the SS non MALT group. Moreover, the limited number of SNPs tested in the *TREX1* gene. Our SNPs were selected from previous studies in lupus and other autoimmune disorders [29, 45, 52]. Despite these limitations, this small-scale preliminary study supports the distinct pathogenetic nature of non-MALT lymphomas in the setting of SS, reinforcing previous data from our group revealing a contributory role of *MTHFR* variants in the pathogenesis of SS related non-MALT but not SS MALT lymphomas [19].

In further studies, our aim is to explore whether *TREX1* exonuclease activity is affected by the presence of the rs11797 *TREX1* gene variant using commercially available 3' to 5' Exonuclease Activity Assays in isolated PBMCs from wild type and mutant carriers. Furthermore, given the implication of *TREX1* in genomic instability [53] -a previously proposed mechanism for lymphomagenesis [54]- intrinsic DNA damage will be assessed using the comet assay in the same samples.

In conclusion, this study supports the role of specific *TREX1* variants in SS related non-MALT lymphoma, possibly through dampened type I IFN production. Undoubtedly, given the rarity of non-MALT lymphoma in the setting of SS, replication of these findings in multicenter studies is definitely needed.

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Contributors:

AN, MKC and CPM conceived and planned the experiments. MV, SG, SDV and CPM recruited patient cohorts. AN, PM and SG contributed to sample preparation. AN and PM carried out the experiments. AN, PM, SG, SDV, MV and CPM gathered data and contributed to the interpretation of the results. AN, PM and CPM prepared the manuscript. MV, MKC and CPM critical read the manuscript. All authors provided critical feedback and helped shape the final version of the manuscript.

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TABLES

Table 1: Distribution of the allelic frequencies of the *TREX1* rs11797, rs3135941 and rs3135945 variants in primary SS patients complicated or not by lymphoma versus HC.

SNP	Allele	HC	SS	SS-lymphoma	1000 Genomes Project Phase 3 (European)	OR *	OR **	OR ***
		(n=240) (%)	(n=229) (%)	(n=89) (%)		[95%CI] p-value*	[95%CI] p-value**	[95%CI] p-value***
rs11797	A	51.3	46.3	43.8	44	0.8 [0.6~1.1]	0.7 [0.5~1.1]	0.9 [0.8~1.25]
	G	48.7	53.7	56.2	56	0.1	0.1	0.6
rs3135941	C	16	18.3	16.3	17	1.2 [0.8~1.7]	1.1 [0.6~1.6]	0.9 [0.6~1.4]
	T	84	81.7	83.7	83	0.4	0.9	0.6
SNP	Allele	HC (n=202) (%)	SS (n=192) (%)	SS-lymphoma (n=65) (%)	1000 Genomes Project Phase 3 (European) (%)	OR * [95%CI] p-value*	OR ** [95%CI] p-value**	OR *** [95%CI] p-value***
rs3135945	G	100.0	99.5	100.0	100.0			
	A	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	na	na	na

OR *, p-value*: HC patients versus SS

OR**, p-value**: HC vs SS-lymphoma patients OR***, p-value***: SS versus SS-lymphoma patients

SS: Sjogren's Syndrome, HC: Healthy Controls, SNP: single nucleotide polymorphism, OR: Odds ratio, CI: confidence interval, na: not applicable.

Table 2: Distribution of the genotype frequencies of the TREX1 rs11797, rs3135941 and rs3135945 variants in primary SS patients complicated or not by lymphoma versus healthy controls (HC). ORs and p-values for additive model are shown.

SNP	Genotype	HC	SS	SS- lymphoma	OR* Additive	OR** Additive	OR*** Additive
		(n=240) (%)	(n=229) (%)	(n=89) (%)	model [95%CI] p-value*	model [95%CI] p-value**	model [95%CI] p-value***
rs 11797	AA	27.5	22.7	22.5	1.25 [0.9-1.7]	1.4 [1.0-2.0]	1.1 [0.8-1.4]
	GA	45.4	47.2	42.7	0.1	0.08	0.6
	GG	27.1	30.1	34.8			
rs 3135941	TT	71.6	69.9	75.3	1.3 [0.9-1.7]	1.1 [0.7-1.7]	0.9 [0.6-1.4]
	TC	24.5	23.6	16.9	0.1	0.7	0.6
	CC	3.9	6.5	7.8			
SNP	Genotype	HC (n=202) (%)	SS (n=192) (%)	SS- lymphoma (n=65) (%)	OR* Additive model [95%CI] p-value*	OR** Additive model [95%CI] p-value**	OR*** Additive model [95%CI] p-value***
rs3135945	GG	100.0	99.5	100.0			
	GA	0.0	0.0	0.0	na	na	na
	AA	0.0	0.5	0.0			

OR *, p-value*: HC patients versus SS

OR**, p-value**: HC vs SS-lymphoma patients

OR***, p-value***: SS versus SS-lymphoma patients

SS: Sjogren's Syndrome, HC: Healthy Controls, SNP: single nucleotide polymorphism, OR: Odds ratio, CI: confidence interval, na: not applicable.

Table 3: Distribution of the allelic frequencies of *TREX1* rs11797 and rs3135941 variants in primary SS patients complicated by MALT and SS non-MALT lymphoma type versus HC.

SNP	Allele	HC (n=240) (%)	SS- MALT (n=70) (%)	SS non- MALT (n=19) (%)	1000 Genomes Project Phase 3 (European) (%)	OR * [95%CI] p-value*	OR ** [95%CI] p-value**	OR *** [95%CI] p-value***
rs11797	A	51.3	47.1	31.6	44	0.9 [0.6~1.25]	0.4[‡] [0.2~0.9]	0.5 [0.3-1.1]
	G	48.7	52.9	68.4	56	0.4	0.02	0.09
rs3135941	C	16	15	21.1	17	0.9 [0.6~1.6]	1.4 [0.6 ~ 3.2]	0.7 [0.3-1.6]
	T	84	85	78.9	83	0.8	0.4	0.7

[‡] 0.4 [0.2-0.8], p-value: 0.008, following adjustment for age and sex

OR *, p-value*: HC patients versus SS-MALT patients

OR**, p-value**: HC vs SS non-MALT patients

OR***, p-value***: SS-MALT versus SS non-MALT patients

SS: Sjogren's Syndrome, HC: Healthy Controls, SNP: single nucleotide polymorphism, OR: Odds ratio, CI: confidence interval

Table 4: Genotypic frequencies of the *TREX1* rs11797 and rs3135941 variants in primary SS complicated by MALT and SS non-MALT lymphoma patients and HC. ORs and p-values for additive model are shown.

SNP	Genotype	HC (n=240) (%)	SS-MALT (n=70) (%)	SS non- MALT (n=19) (%)	OR* Additive model [95%CI] p-value*	OR** Additive model [95%CI] p-value**	OR*** Additive model [95%CI] p-value***
rs 11797	AA	27.5	25.7	10.5			
	GA	45.4	42.9	42.1	1.1 [0.8-1.7]	0.5 [0.2-0.9]	0.5 [0.2-1.1]
	GG	27.1	31.4	47.4	0.4	0.02	0.08
rs 3135941	TT	71.6	77.1	68.4			
	TC	24.5	15.8	21.1	1.0 [0.6-1.6]	1.4 [0.6-2.9]	0.8 [0.4-1.7]
	CC	3.9	7.1	10.5	1.0	0.5	0.6

OR *, p-value*: HC patients versus SS-MALT patients

OR**, p-value**: HC vs SS non-MALT patients

OR***, p-value***: SS-MALT versus SS non-MALT patients

SS: Sjogren's Syndrome, HC: Healthy Controls, SNP: single nucleotide polymorphism, OR: Odds ratio, CI: confidence interval

Table 5. Haplotype analysis of the *TREX1* rs11797 and rs3135941 variants in primary SS non-MALT lymphoma patients versus HC.

Haplotype	HC (n=240) (%)	SS non-MALT (n=19) (%)	χ^2	Fisher's p	Pearson's p	OR (95% CI)
A C	5.8	0	2.3	0.1	0.1	-
A T	45.5	31.6	2.8	0.1	0.1	0.6 (0.3~1.1)
GC	10.3	21.1	4.2	0.04	0.04	2.3 (1.0~5.4)
GT	38.4	47.3	1.2	0.3	0.3	1.4 (0.7~2.8)
Global χ^2 is 8.1. Fisher's p-value=0.04						

SS: Sjogren's Syndrome, HC: Healthy Controls, χ^2 : chi square test, OR: Odds ratio, CI: confidence interval

Figure legends

Figure 1. *TREX1* mRNA expression in peripheral blood (PB) samples and minor salivary gland tissues (MSG). **A.** No statistically significant difference in *TREX1* PB expression was detected between the GG, AG and AA genotypes of the rs11797 *TREX1* variant (mean±SD: 4.3±2.7 vs 4.0±2.6 vs 3.4±2.2, respectively, $p>0.05$ for all comparisons), as well as for the TT, CT and CC genotypes of the rs3135941 *TREX1* variant (mean±SD: 4.1±3.2 vs 3.2±1.5 vs 3.5±3.0, respectively, $p>0.05$ for all comparisons). **B.** *TREX1* PB mRNA expression was significantly higher in SS patients compared to age/sex matched HC irrespective to lymphoma status (SS mean±SD: 3.6±2.1 vs HC: 1.5±0.9, $p= 0.003$, SS-MALT: 4.3±3.0 vs HC: 1.5±0.9, $p= 0.03$ and SS non-MALT: 5.1±4.1 vs HC: 1.5±0.9 $p= 0.04$), while no difference was reported between SS subgroups. **C.** No statistically significant difference in *TREX1* MSG expression was reported between the GG and AG genotypes of the rs11797 *TREX1* variant (mean±SD: 0.4±0.4 vs 1.1±2.6, $p>0.05$), as well as for the TT, CT and CC genotypes of the rs3135941 *TREX1* variant (mean±SD: 0.6±0.9 vs 1.1±1.7 vs 0.13±0.0, respectively, $p>0.05$ for all comparisons). **D.** *TREX1* MSG mRNA expression did not differ significantly between 16 SS, 10 SS-MALT and two age/sex matched sicca controls (mean±SD: 0.8±0.9 vs 0.8±1.4 vs 0.8±0.3, respectively, $p>0.05$ for all comparisons).

Figure 2. Type I interferon (IFN) related genes in 52 peripheral blood (PB) and 26 minor salivary gland (MSG) samples derived from SS patients independently of lymphoma status in association with *TREX1* variants. No significant difference was detected between *IFIT1*, *MX1* and *TRAF3* mRNA expression in peripheral blood samples with different *TREX1* genotypes of the rs11797 and rs3135941 *TREX1* variants ($p > 0.05$ for all comparisons, Figs A-C). Patients sharing the rs11797 AA *TREX1* genotype depicted increased mRNA expression of several interferon related genes such as *IFIT1* ($p < 0.05$), *MX1*, *TRAF3* ($p < 0.05$) and *TRAIL-M* ($p < 0.0001$) in SS MSG tissues compared to the GG genotype (Figs D-G). No statistically significant differences were detected between distinct rs3135941 genotypes and IFN inducible gene expression.

Figure 1
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Figure 2
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Peripheral Blood

Minor Salivary Glands

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TREX1 variants in Sjogren's syndrome related lymphomagenesis

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ABSTRACT

Genetic variants of the three-prime repair exonuclease 1 (*TREX1*) -an exonuclease involved in DNA repair and degradation- have been previously found to increase susceptibility to Aicardi Goutieres syndrome, familial chilblain lupus and systemic lupus erythematosus. We aimed to explore whether *TREX1* common variants could influence the risk of primary Sjogren's syndrome (SS) and SS-related lymphoma. Three single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) of the *TREX1* gene (rs11797, rs3135941 and the rs3135945) were evaluated in 229 SS, 89 SS-lymphoma (70 SS-MALT and 19 SS non-MALT) and 240 healthy controls by PCR-based assays. In available 52 peripheral blood and 26 minor salivary gland tissues from our SS cohort, mRNA expression of type I interferon (IFN) related genes and *TREX1* was determined by real-time PCR. Significantly decreased prevalence of rs11797 A minor allele was detected in SS patients complicated by non-MALT lymphoma compared to controls (OR [95% CI]: 0.4 [0.2-0.9], p-value: 0.02). SS patients carrying the rs11797 AA genotype had increased type I IFN related gene mRNA expression in minor salivary gland tissues. These data support genetically related dampened type I IFN production as an additional mechanism for SS-related lymphomagenesis.

Key words: Three-prime repair exonuclease 1 (*TREX1*), lymphoma, Sjogren's syndrome (SS), single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), genetics

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: